

From LLM Generation to Knowledge Representation: Creating and Structuring the *GeminiKnowledge-sr* QA Dataset for Serbian

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Abstract. LLMs capable of answering questions, fulfilling diverse user requests, and functioning as chatbots rely heavily on extensive datasets. However, for the Serbian language, there is a significant lack of high-quality datasets structured in a question-and-answer (QA) format. To address this gap, we have created the largest QA dataset *GeminiKnowledge-sr* in Serbian, foundational dataset specifically designed to improve QA capabilities in Serbian LLMs, which can work in conjunction with or as an alternative to formal KGs. This dataset is designed to encompass a broad spectrum of knowledge domains, ranging from specialized expert fields to areas concerning sports, culture, personal development, everyday activities, and more. The development started with generation of tree-level taxonomy: Area (26) → Topic (317) → Facet (6376), followed by generation of context, questions and answers. After filtering 127,091 QA pairs remained. In the next phase, the knowledge base question generation involved creation of natural language questions based on structured data, represented as fact triples.

Keywords: Question-Answering · Large language models · Serbian · Knowledge Graphs · Knowledge Representation.

1 Introduction

Recent advancements in AI have significantly propelled Question Answering (QA) technologies, yet resources for languages like Serbian remain underdeveloped compared to major world languages. This work introduces an initiative within the TESLA (Text Embeddings – Serbian Language Applications) project to create extensive Serbian QA datasets. The progress in QA heavily relies on benchmark datasets, which are predominantly available for high-resource languages, often focusing excessively on English [9]. This highlights the need for diverse multilingual and monolingual resources, particularly for languages such

as Serbian [2,3]. While traditional dataset creation involved manual or semi-automated methods, Large Language Models (LLMs) now facilitate the generation of rich QA pairs from text [10].

The Knowledge Base Question Generation (KBQG) involves creating natural language questions based on structured data, usually represented as fact triples. Earlier methods often relied on heavy and sometimes ad-hoc pre- and post-processing steps to manage rare entities and handle unseen properties. Han and colleagues [4] were leveraging pre-training, introducing a new (triple, question) dataset, and incorporating question type information. This method outperformed previous approaches in both standard and zero-shot scenarios. Additionally, the extended KBQG dataset not only improves coverage of knowledge base (KB) properties but also enables more diverse question generation, allowing multiple questions to be created from a single triple. Key areas within QA research include Conversational QA (CQA) focused on multi-turn interactions [12] and Knowledge Graph (KG) QA (KGQA) shifting towards using Wikidata, leading to new benchmarks like the multilingual QALD-10 [11] and developments in KBQG, supported by resources like the code and dataset from [4], available at gitlab. The automatic generation of questions was also based on DBpedia [8]. Non-English KBQA resources include RuBQ, a Russian dataset based on Wikidata [5]. The systematic survey of multilingual KG Question Answering (mKGQA) produced a method taxonomy and formally defined key characteristics [6]. Badenes-Olmedo and Corcho developed algorithm MuHeQA for retrieving the answer from textual content automatically generated from KGs instead of queries over them, by extracting answers from textual summaries created by combining information related to the question from Wikidata and DBpedia [1].

QA datasets span various types: 1) extractive e.g. SQuAD, Natural Questions; 2) abstractive e.g. NarrativeQA, MS MARCO; 3) knowledge base (KBQA) e.g. WebQuestions, MetaQA; 4) conversational (CQA) e.g. CoQA, QuAC; 5) open-domain e.g. TriviaQA; 6) multi-hop e.g. HotpotQA, ComplexWebQuestions; 7) commonsense e.g. CommonsenseQA, Social IQA; 8) multimodal e.g. VQA, TextVQA; 9) domain-specific e.g. BioASQ, MedQA; 10) Code-Related e.g. CoNaLa, CodeSearchNet. The diversity of these datasets is crucial for advancing AI capabilities. The methodology for Serbian QA datasets [10] proposed various methodologies: adapting existing formats like SQuAD [7], extracting data from encyclopedic knowledge, creating a domain-specific dataset from a mining and geology textbook (~5000 QA pairs), and transforming structured Wikidata knowledge into QA pairs.

The lack of Serbian resources motivated this research to speed up development, relying on LLMs and Wikidata KB. In this paper, we present the case study in using LLMs (GPT-4/4o, Gemini Flash 2.0) to automatically generate a large-scale, hierarchically structured QA dataset *GeminiKnowledge-sr*. The aim is to enhance data from structured KGs by providing natural language paraphrases of factual knowledge. The hierarchy of the generated dataset (Area \rightarrow Topic \rightarrow Facet) is a form of lightweight ontology or taxonomy, relevant to KG modeling. The details of the methodology (2), the specific prompts used, the

iterative process involving different LLMs, the challenges encountered, and the data scale achieved will be discussed (3). We will present how the QA format implicitly captures entities and relations, the plan for validation, highlighting the challenges of ensuring quality in large datasets generated by LLMs (4).

2 Methodology

The methodology included the development of a three level taxonomy and QA dataset generation for selected topics using LLMs only, but also DBpedia and Wikidata, coupled with LLMs.

2.1 Generating a QA Dataset using Gemini

The methodology was focused on obtaining the best balance between the sufficient dataset size, on one hand, and the cost of generating the dataset via paid LLM models, on the other. In order to determine the best model for this task, we have conducted manual testing of paid LLM models from the companies OpenAI, Anthropic, and Google by generating sets of questions and answers in Serbian and analyzing the generated text (in January 2025). The criteria in our analysis were the relevancy of the questions and answers to the given prompt, the factual precision of the generated responses, as well as the consistency in using words and expressions in the Serbian language (as opposed to words and expressions in other South Slavic languages). In this period, the GPT-4 model demonstrated the best performance against these criteria.

In the next phase, we chose 20 areas of knowledge that we considered relevant for a wide range of users and for which there was a large amount of publicly available data. For each knowledge area, we generated 20 topics, and subsequently, 3-5 facets (subtopics) for each topic (see Section 3). In this phase, the GPT-4 and GPT-4o models were used. After Gemini Flash 2.0 model was publicly released, our tests showed that it had superior Serbian language competence compared to other models, while maintaining factual accuracy. Furthermore, it offered a free API usage quota, which allowed us to create a large, high-quality, and cost-effective dataset. Thus, the initial dataset structure (created using GPT-4 and GPT4-o) was expanded using the Gemini Flash 2.0 model, resulting in 26 knowledge areas, 317 topics and a total of 6376 facets (with each Topic containing a varying number of facets reflecting its scope).

Following this structural definition, 20 QA pairs were generated for each facet, yielding a total of 127,520 pairs. Python scripts utilizing the OpenAI and Gemini APIs were developed and used for both generating the hierarchical structure and the corresponding QA pairs. After an initial filtering step to remove certain pairs, the dataset currently comprises 127,091 QA pairs. It should be noted that, because some facets were merged to maintain logical hierarchy, and some facets had several invalid QA pairs, not all facets in the dataset have the same number of QA pairs.

To better understand the linguistic characteristics of the dataset, we calculated the minimum, maximum, and average number of words per question and answer, as well as their respective character lengths. These statistics provide insights into the variability and complexity of the generated content. The results are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Length of questions and answers in first experiment.

	Min words	Max words	Avg. words	Min length	Max length	Avg. length
Questions	2	28	9	10	177	60
Answers	11	119	47	69	847	333

These values reflect the natural variation in question formulation and answer elaboration. While some questions are concise and fact-based, others require more descriptive phrasing. Similarly, the length of answers depends on the nature of the expected response, ranging from short factual replies to more detailed explanations. Table 2 presents results of second experiment with three different models: gemini (2.5-flash-preview-04-17), and two OpenAI models: gpt-4.1-2025-04-14 and gpt-4.5-preview using DSPy declarative framework for building modular AI software. DSPy allowed us to build more effective prompts.

Table 2. Length of questions and answers in second experiment.

Model		Min words	Max words	Avg. words	Min length	Max length	Avg. length
gemini 2.5-flash -preview-04-17	Questions	4	14	8	23	86	58
	Answers	1	30	8	5	190	59
gpt-4.1-2025-04-14	Questions	7	26	15	44	148	95
	Answers	2	116	32	20	787	222
gpt-4.5-preview	Questions	5	24	10	33	180	71
	Answers	1	41	12	7	311	87

To evaluate the robustness of each model in retrieving answers from structured data, we issued 100 test queries per model. Figure 1 summarizes the number of generated queries that are syntactically and semantically valid (could be executed without errors) and how many of those yielded actual results. As shown, GPT-4.5-preview demonstrated the highest retrieval success, both in query execution and in returning results.

2.2 Generating a QA Dataset from KB

Using DBpedia and Wikidata offers a robust foundation for generating factual QA datasets. For topic specification, we relied on facets in the previous step (*GeminiKnowledge-sr*). First, we identified the key entities and properties for

Fig. 1. Query success rate and result retrieval for each model, based on 100 test queries.

each defined facet: the relevant types of entities (e.g., for "Hiking," entities could include mountains, hiking equipment, famous mountaineers, hiking clubs). The specific properties in DBpedia (dbo:elevation, dbo:location, dbo:type) and Wikidata (wdt:P2044 - elevation, wdt:P625 - coordinate location, wdt:P31 - instance of, wdt:P17 - country) that contain the desired information to be converted into QA pairs were also identified. The experiments were performed with Wikidata, since it generally offers more structured data, better support for Serbian, and is more actively maintained. To automatize the process, we generated prompts for each facet with a task to generate a SPARQL query that will retrieve related concepts and their most important properties, but we gave a list with properties restrictions that we were not interested in like for image, datatype, IDs in other encyclopedia, etc. The generated SPARQL query would be submitted and error/-success was recorded for future steps. The interaction with Wikidata SPARQL endpoints was direct, we did not use data dump.

The following example illustrates data extraction using SPARQL Query Formulation. The instruction can be given as: “Construct SPARQL queries to retrieve relevant entities and their selected property values for the defined topics/entity types” and the generated query for finding European capitals and their countries would be:

```

1 SELECT ?city ?cityLabel ?country ?countryLabel
2 WHERE {
3   ?city wdt:P31 wd:Q5119 . # instance of Capital City
4   ?city wdt:P17 ?country . # located in ?country
5   ?country wdt:P30 wd:Q46 . # on the continent Europe
6   SERVICE wikibase:label {bd:serviceParam
7     wikibase:language "sr".} # labels in Serbian
8 }

```

Listing 1.1. SPARQL query for European capitals.

Specific queries must be designed for each type of information targeted (e.g., mountain elevation, movie genre). Crucially, queries must request labels for both entities and values in the target language (Serbian), using mechanisms like SERVICE wikibase:label in Wikidata or rdfs:label with language filters in DBpedia.

The formulated queries were executed on a SPARQL endpoint during the preliminary testing phase, but this was later integrated into Python code using libraries. The retrieved results were stored in a structured format (e.g., JSON and ttl). Each record represented a single fact (Entity - Property - Value), including their Serbian labels.

The critical step involves transforming the structured data into natural language questions. For each extracted property, one or more question templates in Serbian were defined. To generate context - QA pair, a hybrid approach was tested. We started with prioritizing Wikidata for structured facts and Serbian labels for output, but next experiments allowed introduction of knowledge from LLM, which gave much better results. Prompts were written in Serbian (Cyrillic script) and submitted to Gemini 2.5 Flash that just appeared during experiments (April 17th 2025).

Templates can range from simple string substitutions to more complex formulations, potentially incorporating logic for grammatical agreement, e.g., gender, very important for Serbian. Here are a few template examples that were explored:

- For wdt:P17 (country): "U kojoj državi se nalazi [Entity Label]?" (In which country is [Entity Label] located?)
- For wdt:P2044 (elevation): "Koja je nadmorska visina planine [Entity Label]?" (What is the elevation of the mountain [Entity Label]?)
- For wdt:P569 (date of birth): "Kada je rođen/a [Entity Label]?" (When was [Entity Label] born?)
- For dbo:capital: "Koji je glavni grad [Entity Label]?" (What is the capital city of [Entity Label]?)

The Python script that iterates through the collected facts (Entity-Property-Value triples) was generated. For each fact, it identifies the corresponding question template based on the property (URI or PID) and substitutes the [Entity Label] with the entity's Serbian label to form the question. The answer was typically the Serbian label of the value extracted from KG. If the value is a literal (number, date, string), it's used directly, potentially applying necessary formatting (e.g., adding units like "meters" for elevation). If the value is another entity (e.g., the country for a capital city), its Serbian label is used as the answer.

Since the template generation was time consuming, we used prompting to let LLM to generate QA relying only on 1) Wikidata and 2) Wikidata and LLM knowledge. The generated pairs were stored in a suitable format as a JSON list of objects, where each object contained area, topic, facet, entity, QID (Wikidata ID), context, question, answer.

3 Results and Discussion

GeminiKnowledge-sr features a hierarchical structure facilitated broad knowledge coverage while also enabling targeted applications focused on specific knowledge areas:

- Knowledge area, the highest level, representing a broad knowledge domain (e.g., "Hobiji i rekreacija" (Hobbies and Recreation), "Ekologija i održivost" (Ecology and sustainability)).
- Topic, as a narrower category within a specific knowledge area (e.g., "Planinarenje" (Hiking), "Klimatske promene" (Climate change)).
- Facet, as the most granular level, detailing a specific aspect of a topic (e.g., "Planinarska oprema" (Hiking Equipment), "Uzroci klimatskih promena" (Causes of climate change)).

The general idea is to map the taxonomy with KGs, in the first step with Wikidata, then with DBpedia and some other. Here is one snippet of the dataset.

```

1 [{ area: "Hobiji i rekreacija",
2    wikidata: [{ QID: "Q47728", label_en="hobby", label_sr="
3                hobi"},{QID: "Q184872", label_en="recreation",
4                label_sr="rekreacija"}],
5    dbpedia: ["dbc:Recreation", "dbr:Hobby"]
6    topics: [{ topic: "Aktivnosti napolju",
7                facets: [{ facet_id:"", facet: "
8                    Planinarenje", QID: "Q36908", label_en:
9                        "mountaineering"}, ... ]
10           }]
11 ]}]

```

Listing 1.2. Sample QA JSON Data

As mentioned before, 20 question and answer pairs were related per facet, as illustrated in the next example.

```

1 [{ area: "Hobiji i rekreacija",
2    topic: "Aktivnosti napolju",
3    facet_id:"", facet: "Planinarenje",
4    QID: "Q36908", entity: "mountaineering",
5    qa: [{context: "Planinarenje je aktivnost koja se može
6            opisati kao vrsta sporta i hobi. Planinarenje je
7            podklasa penjanja.",
8            question: "Da li je planinarenje vrsta sporta?",
9            answer: "Da, planinarenje se smatra vrstom sporta."},
10           {context: "Planinarenje je aktivnost koja predstavlja
11           podklasu penjanja. Smatra se kako vrstom sporta,
12           tako i hobijem. Povezane aktivnosti koje mogu
13           slediti planinarenje uključuju i BASE skakanje.",
14           question: "Kako se može klasifikovati aktivnost
15           planinarenja?",
16           answer: "vrstom sporta, tako i hobijem" } ]
17 ]}]

```

Listing 1.3. Sample QA JSON Data

For questions and answers, only the basic filtering and cleaning were involved: automatic removal of pairs with missing questions or answers, checking for and handling duplicate QA pairs, reducing from 127,520 to 127,091 QA pairs. We

considered filtering out overly trivial questions (e.g., "What is Belgrade an instance of? Answer: Capital city"), potentially by excluding certain properties (like `wdt:P31 - instance of`), for some topics.

A preliminary evaluation of the generated QA dataset was conducted by manually double-checking a sample of 100 question-answer pairs. The selection of the 100 pairs was pseudorandom: for each of the 26 knowledge areas 2 questions were randomly selected within the area itself. The remaining 48 questions were randomly selected from the dataset. The assessment focused on three key aspects: factual correctness, textual quality, and the agreement of the generated content with the specified facet, area, and topic. Since the dataset covers a wide array of topics beyond the evaluators' own knowledge, the evaluators verified the factual accuracy of certain specialized domains by consulting different Internet sources for easily verifiable information, and by using the `o4-mini-high` model (with Web search enabled) in ChatGPT to research and explain the factuality of the answer for more nuanced questions that are not easily verifiable through a manual Internet search, which provided us further context supported with references. It should be noted that the evaluation certainty is slightly lower in those particular instances due to the evaluators' lack of specific domain knowledge. The initial findings demonstrate impressive performance across these criteria, achieving 98% for factual correctness, 91% for textual quality, and 98% for agreement with facet, area and topic. The most common issue encountered was the use of apostrophes as quotation marks, which is incorrect in Serbian orthography (7 examples). Another issue which lowered the score of the textual quality was the use of English or Croatian variants instead of Serbian words (e.g. "Risk" instead of "Riziko" and "parcijalni naboji" instead of "parcijalno naelektrisanje"), as well as a few, seemingly new, Serbian terms which we weren't able to find in use online. For Serbian terminology evaluation, we used the criterion of searching the term with quotation marks in Google search with the restriction "site:ac.rs", which allowed us to review whether the term appeared in any Serbian academic publications. Overall, based on the criteria assessed, this preliminary manual review suggests a high level of quality in the generated dataset concerning linguistic fluency, and especially concerning content accuracy and topical relevance. The detailed assessment of the grammatical correctness and naturalness of the generated Serbian questions and answers is planned for the next phase.

Some experiments were done with LLMs to generate multiple phrasings for the same question (paraphrasing), to enhance the linguistic naturalness of generated pairs, and to generate questions requiring the synthesis of multiple facts (a significantly more complex task). From 200 generated prompt-queries, there was 137 syntactically correct SPARQL queries, but 56 had some results. The quality and existence of Serbian labels in Wikidata/DBpedia can vary. Manual addition/correction or fallback to English labels was necessary, but this is a task for future activities.

Following the extraction of areas, topics, and facets, these terms were translated into English and queried against Wikidata using the `deep_translator` Python library and the Wikidata API. An analysis of the areas (26 total) revealed that

for 6 of them, an English label could not be found in Wikidata. These were typically areas containing a conjunction in their name, such as 'Hobbies and Recreation' or 'Food and Cooking', whereas the individual components (e.g., 'Food', 'Cooking') often existed as separate entries (e.g., Food Q2095, cooking Q38695). In many cases, items that were not successfully linked to a relevant Wikidata entity were found to be recognized as instances of Q13442814 (scientific article) or Q5633421 (scientific journal). For topics (317 total), 37 lacked an English label, and 12 were incorrectly linked to Q13442814 (scientific article). Regarding facets (5908 total), a significant number, 3397, was not found in Wikidata.

The challenges are numerous, but we will name just a few. Some properties may have multiple valid values (e.g., the occupations of a person). A strategy was needed: one question with all answers, multiple questions, or selecting only one answer. Also, public SPARQL endpoints and LLMs often have query rate limits and execution timeouts, so large-scale extraction might necessitate using data dumps or query optimization strategies. Creating effective question templates for a wide variety of properties requires careful design and effort, so the selection of a well-defined topic and a few key properties to test the end-to-end pipeline before scaling up.

4 Conclusion and Future Work

The presented methodology provided a structured approach to generating large-scale QA datasets. The next critical phase involves a thorough validation process, focusing on correcting both linguistic aspects and factual accuracy within the dataset. The potential metrics and methodologies for evaluating the quality and consistency of LLM-generated structured knowledge will be explored with the broader KG community grappling with similar issues. We anticipate that the *GeminiKnowledge-sr* dataset will prove beneficial for various applications, including but not limited to: 1) the instruction fine-tuning by enhancing LLMs to better understand and execute diverse user instructions; 2) Chatbot training by developing more capable and knowledgeable conversational agents for Serbian; 3) Information extraction as a resource or benchmark for extracting structured information from text; 4) KB construction by providing foundational content for building Serbian language KBs. Future work will be focused on automatic extractions of entities and relations from the QA pairs to populate a formal Serbian KG. This positions the dataset as an intermediate representation between unstructured text and a structured KG, generated efficiently using LLMs. We will analyze SPARQL queries that didn't retrieve data to check whether it is because of missing data or other reasons. Future research could explore leveraging graph-based approaches for KG completion, specifically focusing on predicting missing relationships between existing entities and classifying entities into appropriate classes.

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References

1. Badenes-Olmedo, C., Corcho, O.: Muheqa: Zero-shot question answering over multiple and heterogeneous knowledge bases. *Semantic Web* **15**(5), 1547–1561 (2024)
2. Cenić, A.B., Stojković, S.: A Serbian Question Answering Dataset Created by Using the Web Scraping Technique. In: 2023 58th International Scientific Conference on Information, Communication and Energy Systems and Technologies (ICEST). pp. 147–150. IEEE (2023)
3. Cvetanović, A., Tadić, P.: Synthetic Dataset Creation and Fine-tuning of Transformer Models for Question Answering in Serbian. arXiv:2404.08617 (2024)
4. Han, K., Ferreira, T.C., Gardent, C.: Generating Questions from Wikidata Triples. In: Proceedings of the Thirteenth Language Resources and Evaluation Conference. pp. 277–290. ELRA (2022)
5. Korablinov, V., Braslavski, P.: RuBQ: A Russian Dataset for Question Answering over Wikidata. In: Pan, Jeff Z. et al. (ed.) *The Semantic Web – ISWC 2020: 19th International Semantic Web Conference, Proceedings, Part II. Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, vol. 12507, pp. 97–110. Springer (2020)
6. Perevalov, A., Both, A., Ngonga Ngomo, A.C.: Multilingual question answering systems for knowledge graphs—a survey. *Semantic Web* **15**(5), 2089–2124 (2024)
7. Rajpurkar, P., Jia, R., Liang, P.: Know what you don't know: Unanswerable questions for squad. In: Proceedings of the 56th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 2: Short Papers). pp. 784–789 (2018)
8. Rocha, O.R., Zucker, C.F., Giboin, A., Lagarrigue, A.: Automatic generation of questions from DBpedia. *International Journal of Continuing Engineering Education and Life Long Learning* **30**(3), 276–294 (2020)
9. Rogers, A., Gardner, M., Augenstein, I.: QA Dataset Explosion: A Taxonomy of NLP Resources for Question Answering and Reading Comprehension. *ACM Computing Surveys* **55**(10), 1–45 (2023)
10. Stanković, R., Rađenović, J., Ristić, M., Stankov, D.: Creation of a Training Dataset for Question-Answering Models in Serbian (2025), accepted for publication in the 2025 JUDIG Conference
11. Usbeck, R., Yan, X., Perevalov, A., Jiang, L., Schulz, J., Kraft, A., Möller, C., Röder, M., Jmal, D., Collarana, D., Hellmann, S., Maheshwari, G., Faldu, K., Hakimov, S., Benedetti, F., Bulatov, K., Kiselev, D., Kravchenko, D., Logvinov, E.: QALD-10—The 10th Challenge on Question Answering over Linked Data: Shifting from DBpedia to Wikidata as a KG for KGQA. *Semantic Web* **15**(6), 2193–2207 (2024)
12. Zaib, M., Zhang, W.E., Sheng, Q.Z., Mahmood, A., Zhang, Y.: Conversational Question Answering: A Survey. *Knowledge and Information Systems* **64**(12), 3151–3195 (2022)